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THE ROLE OF MOBILE GAMES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: This article considers the most important parts of the preparation of primary school students - motor-cognitive activity, which has a versatile impact on the educational process of children. The main task in increasing the motor-cognitive activity of elementary school students is to master a variety of new exercises.

Key words: elementary school, outdoor games, physical education, schoolchildren, movement, problem.

Introduction: The health of children, the development of their body is one of the main tasks of modern society. Motor activity is a powerful biological stimulus. The main physiological feature of the organism of children is the constant need for movement, this is one of the main conditions for its normal growth and development [1, 2].

The modern development of society has significantly changed the nature of the requirements for human motor abilities and, in this regard, new tasks appear in the field of physical education of the younger generation [3]. As the analysis of literary sources shows, the main problem of physical education is the development of physical education of the child's personality, the success of the process of forming the foundations of a healthy lifestyle depends on this [4, 5, 6]. In the pedagogical process, especially in elementary school, much attention is paid to the requirements for a new thinking of the teacher and special requirements for the organization of education, which should contribute to the formation of the creative personality of the student [7, 8]. This is possible only if each teacher organizes physical education lessons on the basis of a personality-oriented approach, using non-traditional means, forms and methods of organizing sports and recreational activities [9, 10, 11].

Outdoor games and game exercises are the most versatile means of physical education for children. This type of physical exercise is at the highest level of children's interest and can solve the problem of optimizing the motor mode of elementary school students, develop their creative and moral activity [12, 13].

Gaming activity is not always combined with positive emotions, pleasant experiences. Children, unlike adults, do not play to relax [14, 15]. On the contrary, often they, without noticing it, get tired of the games. The reason for the rather

frequent transitions of children from one game to another is the onset of fatigue. The child, as it were, “gets fed up” with the previous game and moves on to another, with a different nature of actions [17]. Lesson forms of classes are convenient for teaching the technique and tactical actions encountered in outdoor games. Using these opportunities, students should be shown expedient and economical game techniques, the most beneficial tactical actions used in various situations typical of individual outdoor games.

Physical education lessons in primary school continue to develop in children the skills and abilities laid down in preschool institutions [18, 19]. These are basic motor abilities, coordination, strength, speed, joint mobility, the ability to play mobile and team games [20]. For example, physical education lessons in elementary grades should help children learn:

- correct breathing and ability to combine breathing with movements;
- complicated types of walking and running;
- run with overcoming obstacles (small objects, running around and jumping over them);
- long jump and high jump;
- tossing and catching the ball with one and two hands;
- throwing the ball at a target from a different distance;
- climbing, crawling and crawling in various ways on the gymnastic bench and wall;
- elements of sports games [21, 22].

However, the main task in increasing the motor-cognitive activity of elementary school students is to master a variety of new exercises. This helps to increase the motor reserve of children and has a positive effect on the development of body functions. Enrichment with movements should occur continuously, that is, at every lesson. Unknown, new movements are given so that children experience new motor sensations.

In the lessons of physical education, "motor trinkets" consisting of new movements can be carried out in a playful way in the process of improving certain skills. Like a “sponge”, children “absorb” any information, and the attitudes of children depend on those who are nearby. If at this age a negative attitude towards physical culture is formed, this perception of the subject and movements, as such, can then remain for life. A huge supply of energy that children at this age have must be directed to a “useful channel”, that is, physical activity.

Like any school subject, physical education has its problems. First of all this is the presence in each class of children with deviations in health. Such students,

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unfortunately, are often simply released from classes, but these children are weakened and even more in need of motor activity. It is necessary for such children to limit the load, but not to deprive them of pleasure in motor activity. The most unpleasant thing for a child is the limitation in movements, the deprivation of the opportunity to play with everyone. But in the lessons of physical education, in addition to the development of motor abilities and skills, the moral and volitional qualities of mutual assistance, mutual assistance, goodwill are formed. An important quality is to be able to empathize, to rejoice not only in one's own successes, but also in the successes of other students.

The education of such important qualities for life as willpower, the ability to overcome difficulties, responsibility for oneself and teammates, courage and many other human qualities. There are no such disciplines in the school curriculum in which such a range of moral qualities can be solved. The most important thing is that all these qualities are brought up with the help of outdoor games. For elementary school children, this is the most affordable and enjoyable way. As soon as adults, teachers, teachers forget about it and focus their attention only on motor abilities and skills, the effect will be opposite. Competition can turn into a feud; the inability to perform the exercise may turn into envy, and for some, a sense of superiority may be strengthened. This happens if sporting achievements are placed above spiritual values.

In addition, physical education lessons are the development of cognitive activity, theoretical knowledge is transmitted in the lessons. This happens simultaneously with motor activity, so the skills, backed up by practice, are acquired much faster and stronger. The game is an activity due to which the formation of personality takes place. Children, like adults, learn the world in the process of activity. Games expand the range of ideas about the world around, contribute to the development of observation, ingenuity, analytical thinking, develop the ability to compare and generalize what they see, thus developing the ability to draw conclusions about the observed phenomena of the world.

Play activities are the favorite pastime of children. At the lessons of physical education in elementary school, interrelated tasks are solved in a complex way: educational, health-improving and upbringing. To manage the educational process, a differentiated approach in practical activities, the teacher must monitor the physical fitness of schoolchildren and the processes of adaptation to the requirements of the school curriculum.

Conclusions. Thus, outdoor games used in the educational process of primary school students will contribute to cognitive activity, the development of motor

abilities, a high emotional component in the lesson only if they are arranged in a certain sequence, depending on the tasks of the lesson. In addition, the teacher of physical culture at each lesson forms the need for regular physical exercises. Such skills are easiest to lay in elementary school, when children perceive everything easily, with delight and pleasure.

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